

Evaluation of PERD: Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference

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In this report, the scientific paper "PERD: Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference" is evaluated regarding its reproducibility. It was analyzed vis-a-vis the experiment design and performance metrics, as well as data and code.

The biggest problem encountered was that only a small sample dataset was provided, and the provided code was faulty and not working properly. Furthermore, the literature review was not performed systematically, and the comparison metrics as well as the baselines used in the article were not sufficiently discussed.

CCS Concepts: • **Information systems** → **Recommender systems**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Evaluation, Reproducibility

1 INTRODUCTION

In this report, the overall structure and reproducibility of the paper "PERD: Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference" will be evaluated.

In order to do this, firstly the scientific structure of the paper will be analyzed, particularly the experiment design and setup including the evaluation metrics. In the next step, the data used in the experiments will be analyzed.

Furthermore, the provided code will be analyzed and transformed to make it run on our machines so that the results can be compared with those reported in the paper. And lastly, a detailed analysis of all the problems found with the previously mentioned steps will be performed and reported in the form of a clear table.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this section, the experimental workflow of the paper discussed will be analyzed. Particularly, the strategies used to obtain results will be discussed and the four sections experiment design, evaluation metrics data and code, will be analyzed.

2.1 Experiment Design

First of all, the authors of the paper looked into related work and discussed previous findings using literature review. They described how the task of emoji prediction can be defined and the way this task has been accomplished thus far.

This is also where we can detect the first problem, because the literature review was not conducted systematically. In order to ensure reproducibility not only of the results of running the code, but also the results of the literature review as well it is necessary to provide the name of the search engines that were used to research the papers as well as the search terms and, in case there are many results for the search terms, limiting parameters like a certain time span or a certain country. This way, you can improve the reproducibility of the paper in general and the one of the literature review in particular.[9, p. 1923]

The paper goes on to give a precise problem statement and describe the text encoder used in the models and the personalized attention which is used to gather dynamic user preferences instead of static preferences. [9, p.

1923f]

In the section "Experimental Setting", the authors describe the models they used for text encoding, which are two different pre-trained BERT-models, for each data set one. However, there is no mention of how the models were pre-trained, which train-test splits were used, and if a random seed was used for the splits or the training process in general.

The performance metrics used for analyzing and comparing the different models are just briefly mentioned in one sentence but not explained. The authors used Precision, Recall, F1-Score and NDCG Scores. The metrics should however be explained briefly, in order to ensure that readers can follow the experiment design as well as understand the results in the tables later on easily.[9, p. 1924f]

Lastly, the authors also conducted an ablation study, meaning they ran their experiments again with a different, simpler setting (i.e. not the dynamic user preference, but a static one) to see whether their model actually achieves better performance than simpler models. [9, p. 1925]

2.2 Evaluation metrics

Metrics used for the evaluation in the paper are precision, recall, f1-score and NDCG.

However, in the tables that represent the experimental results (in a comparison of metrics between PERD and other methods' results) the notations of form like P@5, R@10, N@5 and similar are used (overall all 4 metrics have variation of @5 and @10), without any explanation of what those metrics mean in this specific case. It was needed to convey the additional searching process to figure out what is typically meant under those metrics in the field.

In an information retrieval system that retrieves a ranked list, the top-n documents are the first n in the ranking. [2] For example, the P@5 notation means that precision is measured at the top 5 positions in the ranked list, while R@10 signifies recall at the top 10 positions.

Another encountered issue in terms of evaluation metrics was the NDCG, since it is not as widely recognized as another used measure. It would be beneficial to have brief and explicit explanation of the NDCG metric included in the paper, because it will enhance the overall transparency and understanding of the evaluation methodology.

Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (NDCG) is a ranking quality metric, that compares rankings to an ideal order where all relevant items are at the top of the list and can take values from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates a match with the ideal order, and lower values represent a lower quality of ranking. [7]

2.3 Data

This experiment used two real-world datasets. Sina Weibo (China's largest public social media platform) and Twitter:

- (1) **Weibo dataset:** 1.53 million tweets posted by 98,600 users - 50 unique emoticons.
- (2) **Twitter dataset:** 1.63 million tweets posted by 6500 users - 50 unique emoticons.

The datasets used in the experiment were not provided to us. We only have 4 sample pkl files (each with 216029 cases):

- **ids. pkl:** contains a list of ids (probably each id represents a user)

- **labels.pkl**: contains a list of labels, where each row is a list of numbers. Each number probably refers to a unique emoticon.
- **one_hot_labels.pkl**: contains the one-hot-encoded-labels.
- **text.pkl**: contains a list posts in english (samples could be from Twitter but this is nowhere specified)

2.4 Code

This section undertakes a comprehensive examination of the code associated with the research paper which was provided here [8]. The code exhibits notable strengths, such as its accessibility in a Git repository and a reasonably experimental setup description in the paper itself. However, certain drawbacks exist which makes the code's usability and reproducibility very hard.

While the code is accessible through the Git repository, several shortcomings impact its overall quality. The lack of clear instructions for code execution and the presence of merge conflicts pose significant challenges. The use of Chinese comments adds an additional layer of complexity for non-Chinese-speaking users. Furthermore, the inconsistency in imports and the absence of docstrings for custom functions hinder code understanding. In the code a split into training, test and validation set can also not be spotted as well as the actual data used for the evaluation. Instead a sample data folder is provided where it is not clear what data it contains. Additionally, an unclear environment setup and versioning of the used packages further complicates the reproducibility of the experiments.

To address these issues and enhance the code's usability and reproducibility, following steps were used:

- (1) **Resolve Merge Conflicts**: Resolving the merge conflicts within the code files to establish a clear and accurate version. This step was crucial to get the codebase even running.
- (2) **Translate Chinese Comments**: Translate Chinese comments to English to improve code comprehensibility for a broader audience. This step help to get a better understanding what the code actually does.
- (3) **Create Conda Environment**: Establish a Conda environment with Python 3.6 and install the necessary dependencies, including TensorFlow 1.12, pandas, and scikit-learn. Export the environment configuration to facilitate consistent code execution across different machines. The version for TensorFlow need to be assumed by the used functions in the code.
- (4) **Create Parameter File for Sample Data**: Generate a new parameter file tailored for the sample data. Given the assumption that the sample data structure might resemble that of the Twitter dataset, base the new parameter file on the existing one for the Twitter dataset. Furthermore the imports needed to be adjusted to the new parameter file.
- (5) **Download BERT Model**: Download the required BERT model (8/512 - BERT-Medium) from the BERT repository. With the assumption that the sample data is would use the same model as the Twitter dataset.
- (6) **Label Handling**: As the label dictionary (label_dic.pkl) does not exist for the sample data, set the num_labels parameter to 50. This adjustment aligns with the reported number of emojis, ensuring consistency in label handling.
- (7) **Data Splitting Function**: Create a function for splitting data into training, validation, and test sets within the sample data context. Assuming a standard split ratio (e.g., 70-15-15), integrate this function as a first step in the main file (PERD.py) to streamline the data preparation process.

To execute the fixed code seamlessly, follow these steps:

- (1) Create a Conda environment using the provided environment.yml file.
- (2) Optionally modify variables in the parameter file.
- (3) Run the PERD.py file.

2.5 Baselines used in the evaluation

The performance of the PERD method was compared to 6 other methods: Kim-CNN, libFM, B-LSTM DeepFM, mmGRU and CAPER, but except of referring to the papers that proposed or investigated those methods no explanation was given. In addition, other papers in their research don't use Weibo and Twitter datasets what disables the opportunity to control values represented in the PERD paper. To gain the better understanding of the baseline models, those other papers were explored.

Kim-CNN, the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), a sequence model, which is widely adopted for sentence classification, was proposed in the paper authored by Yoon Kim [4]. Kim-CNN applies convolutional operations to text data, treating it as an image where each word or embedding is treated as a pixel, what allows the model to capture patterns in the input text.

libFM is a software implementation for factorization machines that features stochastic gradient descent (SGD) and alternating least-squares (ALS) optimization, as well as Bayesian inference using Markov Chain Monto Carlo (MCMC). [5]. Overall, the LibFM is designed to be efficient and scalable, and is suitable for large-scale machine learning tasks.

B-LSTM (Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory) is a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture that incorporates bidirectional processing, what allows to capture information from past as well as future contexts for each time step in a sequence. As it was shown in the paper[1], LSTMs outperform humans on the same emoji prediction task, suggesting that automatic systems are better at generalizing the usage of emojis than humans.

DeepFM is a state-of-the-art method which combines the power of factorization machines for recommendation and deep learning for feature learning in a new neural network architecture. The FM part helps model to capture low-order interactions efficiently, while the DNN part captures more intricate patterns and non-linear relationships[3].

mmGRU is a multitask multimodality gated recurrent unit (mmGRU) model to predict the categories and positions of emojis. The GRU is a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) that is designed to capture dependencies in sequential data, while multimodality function is used to incorporate multimodality information such as text, image, ans the multitask framework contributes to leveraging the strong correlations between emoji categories and their positions for improving the performance of both tasks. It was proposed in the paper [11]

CAPER - Context-Aware Personalized Emoji Recommendation model fusing the contextual information and the personal information, with a goal to learn latent factors (such as user preference, user gender, and the current time) of contextual and personal information through a score-ranking matrix factorization framework. Moreover, authors of the paper consider the co-occurrence factors of the emojis which could improve the recommendation accuracy. [10]

3 RESULTS AND TESTING

We conducted our experiments with a carefully designed setup to ensure reproducibility and meaningful results. Our model training consisted of 5 iterations, each using a batch size of 16. We employed the pre-trained BERT Medium Model [6]. For the experiments, we utilized a subset of the sample data, specifically the first 1000 datapoints. This choice allows us to work within computational constraints, because we can't use Google Colab due to the dependence of the old version of TensorFlow. The data was split into training (70%), validation (15%),

and test (15%) sets, following a standard 70-15-15 split ratio. The experiments were conducted on a MacBook Pro 2017 with the following specifications: a 3.1 GHz Dual-Core Intel Core i5 processor, 8 GB of 2133 MHz LPDDR3 memory, and Intel Iris Plus Graphics 650 with 1536 MB capacity.

Following table shows the evaluation for different number of historical post to consider (parameter s) on the test dataset. Additionally, compared to the original paper we also included the run time for the training.

Dataset	s	P@5	R@5	F@5	N@5	P@10	R@10	F@10	N@10	Training Time
Sample	1	0.0833	0.3529	0.1348	0.2632	0.0618	0.5235	0.1106	0.3162	12h
	2	0.0806	0.3412	0.1303	0.2657	0.0646	0.5471	0.1155	0.3338	20h
	4	0.0861	0.3647	0.1393	0.2715	0.0632	0.5353	0.1130	0.3322	41h

Table 1. Evaluation Metrics for the Sample Dataset - Testset

In comparing our results with those from the paper in table 4 [9, p. 1925], we observe differences in experimental setups. While our experiments utilized 5 iterations with a batch size of 16 on a subset of 1000 datapoints, the paper employed 10 iterations on a dataset consisting of 1.63 million tweets. It is unclear from the paper whether the reported values are for the training, validation, or test set. Despite these variations, we can identify similarities in the performance metrics, such as that the deviation between different s parameters are similar to those values reported in the original paper.

4 PROBLEMS FOUND

In this section, the problems found in the experiment design of the paper discussed are analyzed. Typically found problems when trying to reproduce results from a paper can usually be divided into three categories: code or setup difficulties, problems with the data, or problems with the process. The paper "PERD: Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference" faces reproducibility challenges. Code issues include limited accessibility, inconsistent imports, and unclear setup instructions. Data problems involve a lack of complete datasets, insufficient descriptions, and reliance on a small sample dataset. The experimental process is hindered by faulty code functionality, incomplete literature review, and inadequate metric and baseline model explanations. Addressing these issues is essential for improving the reliability and transparency of the research findings. We will provide an overview of the typical problems concerning reproducibility and report whether they occurred in the paper evaluated in this article in table 2.

5 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our analysis of the "PERD: Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference" paper revealed significant challenges in its reproducibility. The paper's experiment design lacked clarity, with a small sample dataset and faulty code hindering our attempts to replicate the reported results. The absence of a systematic literature review and insufficient discussion on comparison metrics and baselines further raised concerns about the paper's reliability. Despite these obstacles, our meticulous efforts to address code-related issues and replicate the experiments shed light on the complexities of the research process. This evaluation underscores the critical need for researchers to ensure the accessibility and clarity of their work, thereby contributing to the overall reliability and advancement of scientific knowledge.

Problem description	Found?
Code/Setup Difficulties	
Code not provided	No
Code partially not provided	Yes
Faulty code provided	Yes
Information about software versions missing	Yes
Specific hardware and software setup necessary	Yes
Data	
Data not provided	Yes
Data partially not provided	Yes
Metadata not provided	No
Process	
Comparison metrics or baseline not discussed	Yes
Experimental setup not described	No
Experiment workflow incomplete	No
Inconsistencies in paper, code and data	No
Results differ significantly	No

Table 2. Overview of typical problems with reproducibility

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